

Synthesis and Antibacterial Activity of 4,6-Dimethyl-3-substituted-aminomethyl-coumarins[†]

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A number of 4,6-dimethyl-3-substituted-aminomethyl- and 3-(picolinyl)aminomethyl-coumarins have been synthesised by chloromethylation of 4,6-dimethylcoumarin and subsequent condensation of the chloro compound with various amines. Their structural assignments are based on chemical as well as spectral studies. Most of the compounds showed good inhibition against *E. coli*, *B. subtilis* and *S. aureus*.

VARIOUS derivatives of coumarin nucleus are found to possess diverse biological activities^{1,2}. Many methyl- and aminomethyl-coumarin derivatives are also known to possess CNS stimulant activity³. The importance of substituted-amino groups is evidenced from their presence in many anti-malarials^{4,5} and antimicrobial⁶ agents. Further, the CNS depressing and antimicrobial activity is known to be higher in coumarins with a pyridyl substituent at position-3 in coumarin ring system^{6,7}. Our earlier studies on Mannich bases of 7-hydroxy-4-phenylcoumarin⁸ and 7-ethoxy-4-methylcoumarin⁹ revealed that introduction of a substituted-amino group in a coumarin ring system enhances its biological activity. These findings have prompted us to synthesise some 4,6-dimethyl-3-substituted-aminomethyl- and 3-(picolinyl)aminomethyl-coumarins with a view to evaluate their antibacterial activity. The title compounds have been screened for their activity against *E. coli*, *B. subtilis* and *S. aureus* *in vitro* by standard method¹⁰.

4,6-Dimethylcoumarin (1) is prepared according to the reported method¹¹. Chloromethylation of 4,6-dimethylcoumarin was carried out¹² to give 4,6-dimethyl-3-chloromethylcoumarin (2), which on further condensation with appropriate amine in dry benzene or absolute ethanol following the method reported earlier¹² yielded the corresponding 4,6-dimethyl-3-substituted-aminomethyl-coumarins (3). The reaction is presented in Scheme 1.

The compounds have been characterised from their analytical and spectral data.

Scheme 1

Experimental

Melting points were determined by open-capillary method on Mel-temp and are uncorrected. IR data (KBr) were obtained with a Perkin-Elmer 983 G spectrophotometer and pmr spectra (CDCl_3) on a Varian A 60-A spectrometer using TMS as an internal standard.

4,6-Dimethyl-3-substituted-aminomethyl-coumarins (3). *General procedure*: A mixture of 2 (0.01 mol) and the appropriate amine (0.012 mol) was dissolved in dry benzene or absolute ethanol and refluxed in a water-bath for 4 h. The resulting solid was filtered and recrystallised either from ethanol or petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°) and benzene mixture. Certain compounds were obtained by removal of the solvent.

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TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUND 3

Compd. no. ^a	$\text{—N} \begin{cases} \text{R}_1 \\ \text{R}_2 \end{cases}$	M.p. ^{**} °C	Yield %
2	—	128–30 ^a	45
3a	Morpholine	135–37 ^b	54
3b	R ₁ = R ₂ = CH ₃	125 ^c	52
3c	R ₁ = Me, R ₂ = Ph	148–50	50
3d	R ₁ = H; R ₂ =	145–47	55
3e	R ₁ = Et, R ₂ = Ph	169–71	48
3f	R ₁ = H; R ₂ = OH, —Ph	254–55	53
3g	R ₁ = R ₂ = n-Bu	225–30	46
3h	Piperidine	115–17	52
3i	R ₁ = H; R ₂ = p-tolyl	165–67	56
3j	R ₁ = R ₂ = OH, —Ph	118–20	54
3k	R ₁ = H; R ₂ = Ph	196–98	59
3l	R ₁ = H; R ₂ = β-phenylethyl	144–46	58
3m	R ₁ = H, R ₂ =	142–45	60
3n	R ₁ = H; R ₂ = p-Cl—Ph	196–98	91

^aSatisfactory C, H and N analyses obtained. ^{**}Lit.^{1,2}: ^a 128°, ^b 137°, ^c 127°.

Results and Discussion

The ir spectra of all these compounds exhibited a strong peak at 1710–1745 cm⁻¹ assignable to lactonic carbonyl of coumarin ring system^{1,3}. The ir spectra of 2 exhibited strong and sharp peaks in the region 650–800 cm⁻¹ for C—Cl stretching frequencies^{1,4}. The absence of these peaks and appearance of new peaks in the region 1175–1390 cm⁻¹ (C—N stretch^{1,5}) observed in the spectra of 3 confirmed the replacement of chlorine by substituted-amino group.

The pmr spectrum of 2 showed the absence of a signal at δ 6.3 for C₃—H proton and exhibited an additional peak at δ 5.0 (C₃—CH₂—Cl). Similar peak was also observed at δ 4.5 (C₃—CH₂—N $\begin{cases} \text{R}_1 \\ \text{R}_2 \end{cases}$) in the spectra of 3. The low electronegativity of nitrogen atom in comparison to that of chlorine^{1,5,16} caused upfield shift of methylene protons in 3 compared to that in 2. The substitution of amino-methyl group at C₃-position in the coumarin ring system is confirmed by ir and pmr spectral data.

Biological screening: Among the compounds synthesised some compounds were screened for their antibacterial activity by the method reported in the literature¹⁰. The gram +ve and gram -ve

bacteria employed for the tests were *E. coli*, *B. subtilis* and *S. aureus*. The compounds were screened at 200 ppm concentration. The inhibition zones were measured and the results are presented in Table 2.

TABLE 2—ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITY OF COMPOUNDS 3

Compd. no.	Zone of inhibition (mm)*		
	<i>E. coli</i> (24 h)	<i>B. subtilis</i> (24 h)	<i>S. aureus</i> (24 h)
3a	+	—	++
3d	++	+	+
3f	—	—	+
3h	+	+	—
3i	—	++	—
3k	—	+	++
3m	+	—	—
3n	+	—	+

*Zone dia: (+) = <10 mm, (++) = >10 mm, (—) = no inhibitory zone.

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